

Assessment of Heavy Metals Contamination Status of Bakolori Dam Surface Water Using Pollution Indices

^{*1}Idris AS, ²Magami IM, ³Ahmed JM, ⁴Gada MA.

¹Department of Applied Sciences Abdu Gusau Polytechnic Talata-Mafara, Zamfara State

²Department of Biology, Faculty of Chemical and Life Sciences UDUS, Nigeria

³Department of Zoology, Faculty of Chemical and Life Sciences UDUS, Nigeria

⁴Department of Geography, Faculty of Social Sciences UDUS, Nigeria

*Correspondence: aminushiituidrismafara@gmail.com; Mobile: +2348065955790

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Abstract

Heavy metal pollution indices are used to rate aquatic systems, which are useful tools for determining the trace and heavy metal content of water. This study was conducted to evaluate the pollution state of Bakolori Dam in Zamfara State. The water was collected from each of the four study sites using 750 ml plastic bottles. Standard operating protocols of the WHO and UNEP were used for determination of the water samples. The findings indicated that there was a significant amount of iron (Fe), with global mean concentrations exceeding the WHO limit. While within acceptable limit's area zink, copper and cadmium. The order of the trace heavy metals' total mean concentrations in mg/l was Fe (12.46 mg/l), Zn (0.39 mg/l), Cu (0.19 mg/l), and Cd (0.03 mg/l). Monthly Pollution Index of the Dam was; Metal Pollution Index reached maximum value in December (MPI= 199.17) and its lowest value in June (MPI=3.99). The Trace Metal Pollution Index (TPI) status indicated that April and June had the highest and lowest values obtained, respectively, at TPI=39.47 and TPI=0.35. In comparison to the wet season (18.54 and 6.54, respectively), the dry season had the highest MPI value (85.43) and the greatest TPI value (12.57). Therefore, it is essential to frequently monitor the dam to make sure the water is suitable for drinking and agricultural practices.

Keywords: Bakolori Dam, Heavy metals, Pollution indices, Surface water

1.0 Introduction

In terms of maintaining human health, water is a crucial natural resource [1]. It is a dynamic system made up of both living and nonliving elements as well as organic, inorganic, soluble, and insoluble materials that make up life support systems. Compared to organic compounds, inorganic chemicals make up a larger fraction of pollutants in drinking water [5]. In addition to inorganic molecules, heavy metals can also be found in minerals, which can disrupt the normal operation of human organs and the nervous system due to their propensity to collect there.

Even at low concentrations, heavy metals are hazardous or deadly metallic elements with a relatively high density [15]. One of the most pressing environmental problems in developing nations today is the contamination of freshwater

bodies by trace metals [11]. The use of fertilizers and pesticides, mining, manufacturing, the discharge of domestic or industrial waste, and coal combustion all contribute to the increased levels of metal compounds in the environment that result from modern human life [27, 16].

Due to the possible toxicity of the metals and their harmful effects on organisms, heavy metal poisoning in aquatic habitats is a worldwide concern [26]. As a result of their lengthy persistence, bioaccumulation, and bio-magnification in aquatic compartments, heavy metals are known to have harmful effects at locations far from the source of pollution [28]. According to Demirak et al. [30] and Carol [8], heavy metals that enter freshwater ecosystems are eventually absorbed into the sediments and may bioaccumulate in benthic animals, which then enter the food chain. According to Seema et al

[24], the level of toxicity is influenced by the type of metal, its biological function, and the kind of organism exposed. Lead, iron, cadmium, copper, zinc, and chromium are the heavy metals in drinking water that are most closely associated with human poisoning. These metals are needed by the body in minute quantities, but they can also be toxic in large doses, making them an important group of environmentally hazardous substances if present [24]. The neurological system and internal organs can be harmed by contaminants including Hg, Cd, As, and Pb since they are very hazardous even at low concentrations and do not biodegrade. The performance of living tissues is also negatively impacted by contaminants including Cu, Fe, Mn, Na, and Zn, which are crucial micronutrients [7]. The addition of these alien substances from the environment is rapidly contaminating most water sources, especially in the Zamfara state. According to Garba et al. [10], some environmental factors, such as salinity, pH, and water hardness, can have a significant impact on the accumulation of heavy metals in living things and harm the environment.

Several researchers have created surface water quality and pollution indices using different applications of the Nations Sanitation Foundation

Water Quality Index (NSFWQI) (Carol et al., [8], including the water quality index (WQI) [12] [23] [24], comprehensive pollution index (CPI) [18], trace metal pollution index (TPI). Research on assessing water quality has mainly compared the concentration of pollutants to the National Surface Water Quality Standard based on water monitoring criteria [18].

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

The Dam is an earth-fill embankment situated in Sokoto state, now Zamfara state in northwest Nigeria at coordinates of 12°30'43"N 6°11'0"E. The construction of the dam began in 1974, was completed in 1978, opened the same year, and its reservoir was filled by 1981 [2]. The reservoir of the dam has a total capacity of 450,000,000 cu.m (450 million cubic meters), with the reservoir covering 8,000 ha and extending 19 km (12 mi) upstream [19].

The catchment area of this dam has major vegetation which led to significance run up after heavy rainfall, the soil is made of gravel and part of which is so rocky which led to the low assimilation capacity of rock surface.

Four sample sites were chosen for the study. Two (2) stations (1 and 2) from the upstream and other Two (2) stations (3 and 4) from the downstream. Four sample plastic bottles were used to collect the water sample at monthly interval for the heavy metal parameters for the period of twelve months.

Sample Collection

The water samples were collected by dipping a 750mls plastic bottle just below the water surface at depth of one meter (1m) for each of the four sampling stations. At each of the sample station, the bottle were first raised three time with water before collection of the sample. The sample water was treated in 2ml Nitric acid for preservation to achieve pH of 2.0 and prevent absorption of metals on to the inner surface of the plastic container.

Sample Analysis for the determination of heavy metals

50ml of the water sample was poured on to 25mls conical flask, then 2mls of perchloric acid was added followed by 4mls of nitric acid, the solution was boiled on the hot plate under fume cupboard

Fig. 1: Map of Bakolori Dam showing location of sampling stations.

for about 10 – 15minutes. Then solution was allowed to cool and filtered it was letter diluted with distilled water to make it up to 50mls volumes.

The heavy metals were analyzed by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometric Analysis, the machine consist of an absorption tube which was dipped into the digestive sample. Then each metal has it respective cathode ray lamp in the AAS machine. Because each metal has its own specific web length of light emission on the AAS machine, where the reading was taking as the concentration of each metal in mg/l (ppm).

Determination of the metal Pollution index

Two metal pollutions indices were used in determining the pollution status of Bakolori Dam; The Metal Pollution Index (MPI) of the water samples in the Bakolori dam was calculated to determine the level of trace metal contamination of the surface water in order to assess the suitability of the water quality for drinking [25] [8]

$$MPI = \sum_{i=1}^n C_i / MAC_i \dots\dots\dots 1$$

MPI = Metal pollution index,
 Ci = is the metal concentration (mg/l) in water sample
 MACi (mg/l) = in the maximum allowable concentration [42] The higher the valve of MPI, the more harmful the water into human health [6]

Table i: Categorization of MPI Values for pollution status [17] [8]

Class	MPI Values	Pollution status
1.	< 0.3	Very pure
2.	0-3-1.0	Pure
3.	1.0-2.0	Slightly affected
4.	2.0-4.0	Moderately affected
5.	4.0-6.0	Strongly affected
6.	> 6.0	Seriously affected

Trace Metal Pollution Index (TPI) was also used to evaluate the trace heavy metals in the Bakalori Dam in order to provide information on the composite influence of the individual element on the totality covered to the quality of the water in the dam. Which was calculated according to the following equation [22]:

$$Q_1 = \frac{T_1}{X_1} \dots\dots\dots 2$$

$$k = I / \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{I}{X_i} \dots\dots\dots 3$$

$$W_i = \frac{K}{X_i} \dots\dots\dots 4$$

$$TPI = \sum_{i=1}^n Q_i W_i / \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \dots\dots\dots 5$$

Where k= proportionality constants
 Xi = The limited concentration of trace metal Number 1 according to the environmental standard
 Wi = The mass ratio of trace heavy metal number i
 Ti = The concentration of heavy metal number i
 n= Total Number of monitoring heavy metal
 The TPI value was categorized into two groups

Table ii: Categorization of TPI Values for pollution status [22]

S/NO	Groups	TPI values	Pollution status
1.	Groups 1	TPI ≤ 1	Non Pollution
2	Group 2	TPI > 1	Pollution

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics was used to compute the mean values and standard deviation of the parameters. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to identify the significant differences between the parameters at 5% level of significant (α=0.05).T- test analysis was used to evaluate the significant difference of the water indices between the rainy season and the dry season in Bakolori Dam The interpretation and analysis of the result were based on tables and correlation coefficient test of the parameters.

Results

The mean concentrations of four heavy metals (Fe, Cu, Zn, and Cd) for each month are shown in Table 1 together with the corresponding standard deviations. The level of heavy metals varies greatly from month to month. For instance, the concentration of iron (Fe) in December was significantly higher than it was in the other months. Overall, among the examined heavy metals, Fe has the highest mean concentration, followed by zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), and cadmium (Cd), which has the lowest. There is significant difference in the concentration of Fe across the months and stations at α=0.05 (p=0.045 and

0.453 respectively),but Zn and Cu showed a statistical significant difference only between months, $\alpha=0.05$ ($p=0.000$,and 0.000 respectively) but no significant difference between stations at $\alpha=0.05$ ($p=0.101$ and 0.408).From the result obtained from Cd, there is no significant statistical difference between months and stations at $\alpha=0.05$ ($p=0.474$ and 0.408 respectively)

Table 2 shows that the total amount of iron (Fe) in the water from Bakolori Dam (12.46mg/L) is higher than the acceptable range for drinking

water specified by the World Health Organization WHO. The European Union (EU) has established a range of allowed values, and the overall mean concentration of copper (Cu) in the water from Bakolori Dam (0.19 mg/L) falls within that range. The overall mean content of zinc (Zn) in water from Bakolori Dam was 0.39 mg/L, which was below the WHO-established permitted threshold range. The overall mean Cadmium (Cd) concentration in Bakolori Dam water (0.03 mg/L) was higher above the United States' permitted value range.

Table 1: Monthly mean Concentration of Heavy Metals in Bakolori Dam

Month	Fe	Cu	Zn	Cd
Nov	1.66 ± 0.45804	0.78± 0.2053	1.36± 0.3433	0.01± 0.0130
Dec	55.66± 61.5409	0.25± 0.04	1.21± 1.1070	0.02± 0.0083
Jan	9.94± 19.94	0.18± 0.0424	0.28± 0.0919	0.008± 0.0043
Feb	10.60 ± 7.5945	0.19± 0.0369	0.35± 0.0515	0.003± 0.0043
March	27.49 ± 14.2911	0.19± 0.0083	0.37± 0.16	0.06± 0.0043
April	11.18± 4.7773	0.30± 0.1581	0.42± 0.1762	0.12± 0.2079
May	0.35± 0.3430	0.03± 0.0158	0.04± 0.0164	0.003± 0.0043
June	1.15± 0.6895	0.013± 0.0043	0.03± 0.0120	0.00± 0
July	0.62± 0.7752	0.05± 0.0192	0.08± 0.03110	0.008± 0.0433
Aug	4.74± 3.91478	0.033± 0.0164	0.05± 0.0259	0.008± 0.0433
Sept	2.11± 2.7445	0.17± 0.0886	0.29± 0.1372	0.02± 0
Oct	14.03± 14.2518	0.08± 0.0236	0.18± 0.1088	0.043± 0.0335
Overall mean value	12.46	0.19	0.39	0.03

Values are mean ± standard deviation

Table 2: Comparison of Mean Concentrated Values of the Heavy Metals in Bakolori Dam Surface Water with Some Environmental Standard.

Parameter	Overall mean concentration value	Permissible value	Source
Fe (mg/L)	12.46	0.29 - 0.3	WHO, (2022), NSDWQ, (2015)
Cu (mg/L)	0.19	1.5 -2.0	WHO, (2017)
Zn (mg/L)	0.39	3.0	WHO, (2008), NSDWQ, (2015)
Cd (mg/L)	0.03	0.003	WHO, (2017), NSDWQ, (2015)

The findings of this investigation showed that Fe and Cd concentrations were higher than allowed throughout the study period, with the exception of February and May, when Cd concentrations were exactly within allowed limits (0.003Mg/l).Throughout the research period, the concentration of Cu and Zn was below the permitted standard (Table 2).

Except for the month of June, where there was moderate pollution in the case of the MPI index value and no pollution in the case of the TPI index value, the results of the pollution indices used in

this study showed a higher contamination of these heavy metals (Fe, Zn, Cu, and Cd) throughout the study period (Table 4).

The four heavy metals' overall mean concentrations at the various locations (Station I, Station II, Station III, and Station IV) are shown in Table 5.The two elements with the highest concentrations in the station are Fe and Zn. In comparison to other stations, station III has the highest concentration of Fe, followed by station Cu, station Zn, and station II, and station IV for Cd.

Table 3: Overall Mean Concentration of Heavy Metals by Stations

Heavy Metal	Station i	Station ii	Station iii	Station iv
Fe	9.29	21.50	9.51	9.55
Cu	0.16	0.19	0.24	0.16
Zn	0.41	0.52	0.34	0.25
Cd	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.06

The findings of the pollution indices were shown in table 4, with the MPI index recording the highest pollution index of 199.17 in the month of December and the TPI index recording the highest pollution index of 39.47 in the month of April. In the month of June, the two indices' lowest values were 3.99 and 0.35, respectively (table 4). The dry season had the highest seasonal contamination status (MPI index: 85.43; TPI index: 12.57); the rainy season had the lowest seasonal contamination status (MPI index: 18.54; TPI index: 6.54) (table 6). There's a significant difference between dry and rainy season in terms of the MPI value at $\alpha=0.05$ ($p=0.206$), the same significant difference exist between dry and rainy season in terms of TPI value at 5% level of significant when $\alpha=0.05$ ($p=0.216$) The periodical rainfall that diluted some metal concentrations during the wet season may be the cause of the

high contamination factor that was found for all indices during the dry season. Both pollution indices show a tendency to be greater in the dry season than the wet season. The pollution sources upstream may be to blame for the current state of the environment. The increase in water value and improved dilution capacity resulted in a low pollution level during the wet season.

According to the correlation matrix, all of the parameters (Fe, Cu, Zn, and Cd) are positively connected, therefore as one parameter rises, it influences the rise of the other in the following passion. Fe has a poor link with Cd and a somewhat good interaction with Zn ($Zn=0.4998$ (0.5)). Cu and Zn have a strong positive correlation of 0.8571 (0.9), while Cu and Cd have a poor correlation of 0.1467 (0.1) and Zn and Cd have a weak correlation of 0.0528 (0.1). (Table 5).

Table 4: Monthly MPI and TPI Contamination Status of Bakolori Dam

Month	MPI value	Contamination status	TPI Value	Contamination status
Nov	10.03	Seriously Affected	3.35	Pollution
Dec	199.17	Seriously Affected	8.56	Pollution
Jan	71.64	Seriously Affected	3.35	Pollution
Feb	37.79	Seriously Affected	1.36	Pollution
March	115.04	Seriously Affected	20.70	Pollution
April	7.89	Seriously Affected	39.47	Pollution
May	11.23	Seriously Affected	9.88	Pollution
June	3.99	Moderately Affected	0.35	Nerve Pollution
July	4.89	Seriously Affected	2.66	Pollution
Aug	19.05	Seriously Affected	2.80	Pollution
Sept	6.95	Seriously Affected	6.88	Pollution
Oct	65.16	Seriously Affected	16.94	Pollution

Table 5: Correlation Matrix of the Heavy Metals in Bakolori Dam

Parameters	Fe	Cu	Zn	Cd
Fe	1			
Cu	0.077142	1		
Zn	0.499829	0.857088	1	
Cd	0.19853	0.146729	0.05277	1

Table 6: Seasonal contamination status of Bakolori Dam

Index	Dry season x	Rainy season x
MPI	85.43	18.54
TPI	12.57	6.54

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study indicate that Bakolori Dam in Talata Mafara, Zamfara State, Nigeria, contains four heavy metals: iron (Fe), zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), and cadmium (Cd). The order of the heavy metals' relative abundance was Fe>Zn>Cu>Cd. Overall, it was found that, with the exception of Fe and Cd, whose concentrations above the permissible limit, all of the tested sites' heavy metal concentrations fell within the range allowed by WHO [30], criteria for drinking water. This supports the findings of Ameen et al. [4] who stated that all heavy metals in the examined sites were within the acceptable limit with the exception of Cd in Duhok Dam, Kurdistan area of Iraq.

When the Zn concentrations in all of the tested sites were compared to the standards from the current study, they were all much below the allowable levels. This supports research by Amalia et al. [3] in Indonesia and Ameen et al. [4] in Iraq, both of which discovered low concentrations of Zn.

In the current study, zinc levels were below acceptable levels whereas copper levels were within acceptable ranges. This might be a result of the sparse mining and industrial activity in the vicinity of the sampling regions. This is in contrast to the findings of Ameen et al. [4], who reported lower values at site 6 during the dry season and higher concentrations of Cu at site 3 during the wet season. However, not all samples of ground water and surface water in Maiganga, Gombe State, contained Cu, according to Hammani et al. [13].

Ameen et al. [4] observed elevated Cd levels in the Duhok dam in Iraq, which was linked to high levels of tourist-generated solid and liquid waste and raised concerns among locals and government officials. Similar to that, the overall mean value of Cd in the Bakolori dam was greater in the current study.

In the present assessment, the greatest contamination status—85.43 and 12.57 for the MPI index and TPI index, respectively—was reported in the dry season. This might be because of seasonal rainfall, which may have diluted some of the metal concentration during the wet season. Both indices' pollution levels tend to be higher in the dry season than in the wet, which may also be related to pollution sources upstream. This is

consistent with the findings of Addey et al. in Lagos, Nigeria, and Ameen et al. [4] in Iraq, who linked the high HPI to the research area's contamination with extremely high levels of heavy metals.

Conclusion

Two pollution indices, the MPI index and the TPI index, were employed in this study to evaluate the heavy metal pollution level in the water and its acceptability for drinking and domestic use. However, based on individual heavy metal criteria, all of the selected heavy metals' concentrations fell below set limitations in accordance with WHO [30] guidelines, with the exception of Fe and Cu. Due to anthropogenic activities, such as agriculture near dams or the discharge of waste items that include high levels of Cd, there may be contamination of this metal at some stations due to increased concentrations of Fe.

The surface water of the Bakolori Dam in the studied area is contaminated, according to the MPI and TPI pollution indices results reported in this research paper. As a result, it is believed that the water cannot be consumed without any prior treatments.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were offered in light of the study's findings:

- i. It is strongly advised that both government organizations and private citizens purify the water before drinking, either by adding chlorine or by boiling and filtering.
- ii. It is important to deter indiscriminate local miners.
- iii. A monitoring team should be established with the mandate to periodically assess the water quality.
- iv. A straightforward physical procedure like filtration Reduced heavy metal loading will result in a clean and safe water supply, hence granular activated carbon filtering of the study spring water is desirable.
- v. To prevent the concentration of heavy metals from entering the dam's water body, the government and authorities should implement effective management programs, such as limiting the overuse of fertilizer and other agricultural inputs in farms near the dam, managing the wastewater and waste disposal

of the nearby village, controlling erosion by re-vegetating the area and building check dams, and providing trash cans near the dam for visitors.

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